
Adsorption Studies of *Delonix regia* Seed Pods and Bambara Ground Nut Shell on Methylene Blue Dyes as Contaminant

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Abstract *Delonix regia* seed pods (DRSP) were obtained from the campus of Federal University Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria and Bambara Ground Nut Shells (BGNS) *Vigna subterranea* fruit hulls were obtained from a farm in Dutse Local Government Area of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The seed pods and fruit shells were washed with water, air-dried, pulverized and sieved into fine particles. The fine particles derived from *Delonix regia* seed pods and Bambara Ground Nut Shells were stored in air-tight containers and labeled DRSP and BGNS respectively. These powdered samples were used as adsorbent on methylene blue dyes contaminant to replace commercially expensive chemical adsorbent. The adsorption power at various pH, wavelength of maximum absorption at various pH, point of zero charge (pzc), effect of pH, effect of ionic strength, effect of contact time, kinetic and equilibrium studies were all carried out for the samples. Both DRSP and BGNS were found to be efficient in removal of methylene blue dye at pH of 8 and 11 respectively.

Keywords *Delonix regia* seed pod (DRSP), Bambara ground nut shell (BGNS), Point of zero charge (PZC) Methylene blue dye, Adsorbent, contaminant

Introduction

Highly colored waste products are produced in large scale by the textile industry and the other organic base industries. The processes of removal of dyestuff from industrial wastewater include adsorption, oxidation-ozonation, biological processes, coagulation-flocculation, and membrane processes [1]. Adsorption appeared to be a key process for the removal of dyestuff among the processes mentioned [2]. The concentration of the dyestuff present in the wastewater needs to be reduced by using adsorbents such as activated carbon, peat, chitin, clay, and others. A process or method by which atoms, molecules or ions are retained on the surfaces of solids by chemical or physical bonding is called adsorption. Adsorption is one of the methods of removal of dyes from water at low cost.

One of the most widely used adsorbents is the activated carbon due to its high adsorption capacity and the fact that it can be produced from renewable and non-renewable resources [3-4]. Due to the environmental and economic reasons, there has been a surfeit of research on the efforts to employ various lignocellulose materials for the production of low cost activated carbon [5].

Despite the frequent use of adsorption in wastewater treatment systems, commercially available activated carbon remains an expensive material. Therefore, using agricultural by-products as adsorbents for the removal of dyes (methylene blue) from waste solutions has been on the increase. This is due to the fact that agricultural by-products are naturally occurring; therefore, they are available at least or no cost [6]. Some of these by-products are

Bambara ground nut shell (*Vigna subterranean*) and *Delonixregia* seed pods from which activated carbon can be prepared.

In previous years, several investigations have been reported the removal of dyes using activated carbons developed from industrial and agricultural wastes [7]. Also using adsorbents from natural materials several studies of dye removal were carried out.

In this study, attempt powder from Bambara ground nut shell (BGNS) and *Delonixregia* seed pods were used directly without preparing activated carbon so as to make the research unique from the previously existing literature. *Delonixregia* seed pods (DRSP) belongs to royal Poinciana or flamboyant which is a member of bean family and produces brown woody seed pods purely a waste material. [8].

2. Material and methods

Delonix regia seed pods (DRSP) were obtained from the campus of Federal University Dutse, Jigawa State, Nigeria and Bambara Ground Nut Shells (BGNS) *Vigna subterranea* fruit hulls were obtained from a farm in Dutse Local Government Area of Jigawa State, Nigeria. The seed pods and fruit shells were washed with water, air-dried, pulverized and sieved into fine particles [9]. The fine particles derived from *Delonix regia* seed pods and Bambara Ground Nut Shells were stored in air-tight containers and labeled DRSP and BGNS respectively.

2.1 Chemicals

Chemical used are of pure and analytical grade they are listed as follows:

Stock solution of methylene blue (1000mg/l) this was prepared by dissolving 1g of solid methylene blue in a 250cm³ beaker, the resulting solution was transferred to 1000cm³ volumetric flask and diluted to the mark.

Stock solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1M NaOH) prepared by weighing 4g of NaOH in a 250 cm³ beaker followed by water, the resulting mixture was transferred to 1000cm³ volumetric flask and diluted to mark.

Stock solution of sodium trioxonitrate (2M NaNO₃) was prepared by dissolving 170g of NaNO₃ in to the 250cm³ beaker containing water then the resulting mixture was diluted to volume in 1000cm³ volumetric flask.

Stock of nitric acid (HNO₃) were prepared, 6.34cm³ of concentrated nitric acid was transferred to 250cm³ beaker containing water, the resulting solution was transferred to 1dm³ volumetric flask and diluted with distilled water to volume.

2.2 Method

The adsorbent were characterized by taking a parameter at a time.

2.2.1 Point of zero charge

The points of zero charge (PZC) of DRSP and BGNS were determined using solid addition method [9-10]. In this method, 1.0 g of DRSP or BGNS were added to twelve 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks containing 50 cm³ of aqueous solution each. Prior to transferring these aqueous solutions into the 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks, the ionic strengths were adjusted to 0.1 moldm⁻³ by adding appropriate amount of 1.0 moldm⁻³ KNO₃ while the pH values were adjusted to values ranging from 2.00 to 12.00 by adding appropriate amounts of 0.1 moldm⁻³ HNO₃ solution or 0.1 moldm⁻³ NaOH solution. The flasks were then stirred at high speed for 5 hours using Magnetic Stirrer hot Plate 78-1 Pecmedical USA. Thereafter, the pH values of the supernatants were measured using pH meter PEC MEDICAL USA (PHS-25) STD. The difference between the initial and final pH was calculated using equation (1). Plots of ΔpH against pH_i were constructed and the points of interception on the pH_i axes gave values of PZC for DRSP and BGNS.

$$\Delta\text{pH} = \text{pH}_f - \text{pH}_i \quad (1)$$

Where pH_i = Initial pH of the solution and pH_f = final pH of the solution.

2.2.2 The wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max})

The wavelength of maximum absorption (λ_{max}) was determined at various pH (ranging from 2-11) using solid addition method [10]. The aqueous of 100cm³ were prepared by transferring 20cm³ of 50mg/l methylene blue to 100cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks then 9cm³ and 9.9cm³ of NaNO₃ for pH 2 and 3 respectively, 10 cm³ for pH 4 to 11 were added and finally, appropriate amount of NaOH and HNO₃ was also added to adjust the pH to 50cm³ of each (of 10)

solution 1g of DRSP was added and the solution were stirred using MAGNETIC STIRRER HOT PLATE 78-1 PEC MEDICAL USA for 5 hours same for BGNS, the procedure was repeated for DRSP and the absorbance (ABS) at various wavelength were taken using 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER Operational voltage 220v.

Percentage (%) removal of methylene blue was calculated using equation (2), by taken the initial and final absorbance at different λ_{\max} of each of the pH mentioned above.

$$\% \text{ removal} = \frac{c_i - c_e}{c_i} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

Were c_i = absorbance of methylene blue before adding the sample, c_e = absorbance of methylene blue after sample was added.

2.2.3 Effect of pH

The effect of pH on the amount of methylene removal was analyzed between the pH range of 2-11 20cm³ of 50 mg/l methylene blue solution was transferred into a 250cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks each containing appropriate amount of NaNO₃ and 1g of Bambara groundnut shells (BGNS) were added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature using for 5 hours. The supernatant solution was filtered. The filtrate was analyzed using the 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER Operational voltage 220v. Adjustment of pH was done with HNO₃ and NaOH optimal condition was selected. The procedure was repeated for *Delonix regia* seed pods (DRSP).

2.2.4 Effect of Ionic Strength

Effect of ionic strength was studied at varying initial concentrations (0.2-1.6). pH was adjusted to 8, this were done by transferring 20cm³ of 50mg/l methylene blue to 250cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks and then 1 μ L of NaOH and diluted to volume. 1g of *Delonix regia* Seed Pods was added to each 50cm³ of above prepared solution. Shaking was done using MAGNETIC STIRRER HOT PLATE 78-1 PEC MEDICAL USA for 5 hours, the supernatant solution was filtered and the filtrate was analyzed using 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER operational voltage 220v selection of optimal condition was done. For BGNS sample, 1000 μ L (pH=11) of NaOH were used [11].

Percentage removal of methylene blue contaminant was determined using equation (2) above, the initial as well as final absorbance was recorded.

2.2.5 Effect of contact time

Effect of contact time was studies at varying the time (from 20-360 min.) the pH and ionic strength was adjusted to 8.0 and 1.6 M respectively, 20cm³ of 50mg/l methylene blue were added to the same flask and 1.0g of DRSP were finally added to 50cm³ of each solution above. For BGNS pH and the ionic strength was adjusted to 11 and 0.6 M respectively. Each flask was then shake at high speed for 20 min, 40 min ... as mentioned above using MAGNETIC STIRRER HOT PLATE 78-1 PEC MEDICAL USA. The solution were filtered using Filter Paper Qualitative Circles (Whatman) cat no. 1000 125, K1597139B 125mm and the absorbance of the filtrates was determined using 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER Operational voltage 220v.

2.2.6 Effect of Adsorbent Dosage

Here the adsorbent dosage was adjusted (from 1.0 – 5.0g) and all other parameters are held at optimal condition i.e. pH =8 (1 μ l of 0.1 M NaOH), ionic strength= 1.6 M (80 cm³ of 2 M NaNO₃), time contact =360 min, methylene blue concentration = 50mg/l (20cm³) and at ambient temperature (28 °C) in a 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks and shake for about 5 hours using MAGNETIC STIRRER HOT PLATE 78-1 PEC MEDICAL USA. The solution was then filtered using Filter Paper Qualitative Circles (Whatman) cat no. 1000 125, K1597139B 125mm. The absorbance of the filtered was obtained using 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER Operational voltage 220v.

2.2.7 Investigation of Sorption Kinetics

Experiment for sorption kinetic study was carried out by adding 1.0 g of DRSP or BGNS to eight 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flasks containing 50 cm³ of dye solutions. The concentration of methylene blue in each flask was maintained at a value of 50 mg/L while the pH and ionic strength of each solution were adjusted to optimal values of 8.0 and 0.1 M respectively. The flasks were then shaking at ambient temperature (28 °C) for specific periods of time (20, 40, 60, 80, 120, 160, 200, 240 minutes) using MAGNETIC STIRRER HOT PLATE 78-1 PEC MEDICAL USA at high speed. The content of each flask was filtered and the residual concentrations of methylene blue in these filtrates were determined at 710 nm using 752N UV-VIS SPECTROPHOTOMETER Operational voltage 220v. The amount of methylene blue adsorbed onto the adsorbent at various time intervals was calculated using equation (3).

This experiment was carried out twice and the fitness of the average data obtained was tested using intraparticle diffusion model (equation 4), pseudo-first order model (equation 5) and pseudo-second order model (equation 6).

$$q_t = \frac{V}{m}(C_i - C_t) \quad (3)$$

$$q_t = k_{int} t^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

$$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1}{2.303}t \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{1}{q_e}t \quad (6)$$

3. Results and Discussion

Several analysis were carried out on both the DRSP and BGNS samples such analysis include point of zero charge determination, UV-Visible (for λ_{max}), effect of pH, effect of contact time, ionic strength and investigation of kinetics studies.

3.1 Point of zero charge (PZC)

The point of zero charge of DRSP and BGNS adsorbent was determined by plotting a graph of change in pH (Δ pH) against initial pH (pHi) as in fig 1 and 2, this was found to be at pH= 7.77 and pH= 7.30 for DRSP and BGNS respectively (see figure 1 and 2). At room temperature (28°C) and normal atmospheric pressure an aqueous solution of DRSP and BGNS with ionic strength of 0.2mol/dm³, has a surfaces charges of zero point at pH of 7.77 and 7.30 respectively. The repercussion of these findings is that, at pH values below this Point of Zero Charge (pzc), the surface charges of the adsorbents are positive while at pH values above this Point of Zero Charge (pzc), the surface charges of the adsorbents are negative [12]. Point of zero charge reported in literature for adsorbents derived from the Agricultural wastes are as follows; Bean Pod was found to be 3.00 [9], 7.10 for oil palm fruit fiber [13], 5.00 for sugarcane bagasse [14], 6.00 for water melon shell [15] and 4.18 for orange peel [16].

3.2 The λ_{max}

Wavelength of maximum absorption of DRSP and BGNS at various pH were obtained from the plot of absorbance against wavelength, λ (nm) as follows; for DRSP 500nm at pH 2, 540nm at pH 3, 660nm at pH 4, 760nm at pH 5, 700nm at pH 6, 540nm at pH 7, 780nm at pH 8, 540nm at pH 9, 540nm at pH 10, and 710nm at pH 11 as in fig 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 respectively. Among which 780nm was found to be the λ_{max} for DRSP at pH 8 suitable for this research work. In other word, the wavelength at which the maximum absorption of methylene blue dyes takes place at optimal condition room temperature (28 °C), normal atmospheric pressure, pH 8 and contact time 5 hours were considered.

For BGNS, the λ_{max} was found to be 540nm at pH 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 710nm at pH 11 as in fig 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22 and 23 respectively. 710nm was considered to be the λ_{max} for BGNS that is absorption at pH 11.

Note: BGNS λ_{max} was constant all through 2 to 10. This may suggest that BGNS may have λ_{max} bigger than 710nm at pH higher than 11 like 13-14 pH. Other literature shows that the λ_{max} for Adsorption of Crystal Violet Dye Using *Leucaena Leucocephala* (Subabul) Seed Pods as an Adsorbent [17] takes place at pH 11 λ_{max} 590nm, Direct yellow dyes has a λ_{max} of 430nm and Direct blue 6 dyes λ_{max} 900nm [6]. Implication of this finding is that, at pH 8 and pH 11, the removal of methylene blue dyes in an aqueous solution reaches the maximum with the % removal of 97.27% and 95.32% for DRSP and BGNS respectively, as such by applying these two low cost agricultural by product we achieved the removal of toxic dyes waste from the aqueous solution.

3.3 Effect of pH

The pH of solution has influence on the extent of removal efficiencies of Methylene blue by DRSP and BGNS at different pH values as shown in table 3.1 and 3.2. From the mentioned tables, it is observed that methylene blue is removed more effectively in slightly alkaline range. The pH 8 and pH 11 are the most favorable pH for removal of methylene blue contaminant by DRSP and BGNS. This two nearly alkaline condition, are considered to be the optimal condition of pH throughout this research project. The finding also reveals that, the removal of methylene blue contaminant increases with the pH from 2-8 and relatively (near constant) decreases from pH 8-11.

The implication of this finding is that, the removal of toxic contamination specifically methylene blue can be achieved by using low cost material (agricultural waste) DRSP and BGNS at pH8 and pH11 (97.27% and 95.32%) respectively. Literature reveals some of the agricultural waste are used as adsorbents for removal of contaminant; Groundnut shell pH 7.0 being optimum [18] for *Vigna subterranea* in biosorption of Cu(II) pH 6.0 is the optimal condition [19]. pH 11 is optimal for Activated Carbon Prepared from the Cryogenic Grinding of Used Tires [20], the exhibited favorable monolayer sorption of denatonium ions from a pH 6.95[21].

Figure 1: Graph of ΔpH against pH_i for DRSP

Figure 2: Graph of ΔpH against pH_i for BGNS

Figure 3: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for DRSP at pH 2

Figure 4: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for DRSP at pH 3

Figure 5: Graph of Absorbance against, λ (nm), for DRSP for DRSP at pH 4

Figure 6: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for DRSP at pH 5

Figure 7: Graph of Absorbance against, λ (nm) for DRSP at pH 6

Figure 8: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for DRSP at pH 7

Figure 9: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm) for DRSP at pH 8

Figure 10: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm) for DRSP at pH 8

Figure 11: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm) for DRSP at pH 9

Figure 12: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm) for DRSP at pH 11

Figure 13: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 2

Figure 14: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 3

Figure 15: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 4

Figure 16: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for bgns at pH 6

Figure 17: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 7

Figure 18: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 8

Figure 19: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 9

Figure 20: Graph of Absorbance against λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 10

Figure 21: Graph of Absorbance against Wavelength, λ (nm), for BGNS at pH 11

3.3 Effect of contact time

The effect of contact time on adsorption of DRSP and BGNS was investigated from 20-420min (0.33 to 4 hours). Fig 22 and 23 shows the effect of contact time on the adsorption of methylene blue dyes contaminant. The percentage removal of methylene blue increased with an increase in contact time. The rate of adsorption is higher in the beginning due to a large available surface area of the adsorbent (DRSP and BGNS). The fast initial uptake is also due to the rapid accumulation of methylene blue on the surface of the adsorbent, as these sites become exhausted the uptake rate will be controlled by the rate at which the adsorbate is transported from the exterior to the interiorsites of the adsorbent particles, hence more time will then be consumed on diffusion of methylene blue to binding sites. However, it remained constant after an equilibrium time of 240 and 360 min for DRSP and BGNS respectively, which indicates that the adsorption had reached saturation. Therefore, the adsorption time was set at 240 and 360 min respectively for DRSP and BGNS in each of the next experiments. Further increase in time after 240 and 360 min respectively for DRSP and BGNS did not bring about any improvement. This is in agreement with the work done in similar literature [22]. The kinetics studies will takes place before the 240 min and 360 min respectively for DRSP and BGNS, the equilibrium studies will takes place above the mentioned time.

Figure 22: Plot of time (minute) vs % removal for DRSP

Figure 23: Plot of % removal vs Time (minute) FOR BGNS

3.4 Effect of ionic strength

Table 3 and 4 shows the effect of initial concentration (ionic strength) on the adsorption of methylene blue dyes contamination. At low concentrations, methylene blue is adsorbed by specific active sites. At higher concentrations; higher adsorption is observed, but at extremely higher concentration, lower adsorption is observed due to the saturation of adsorption sites. An increased in percentage removal of methylene blue may be attributed to sufficient adsorbent surface area to accommodate all methylene blue molecules available in solution. Although the ionic strength is directly proportional to the adsorption (% removal), 1.6 M (1.6mol/dm^3) is considered to be the optimal for DRSP and 0.6 M (mol/dm^3) for BGNS due to the fact that at 1.6 M (NaNO_3) the % removal is high about 82.97% DRSP and 0.6 M (NaNO_3) the % removal is high about 77.29% which are considered to be the bench mark (optimal) for DRSP and BGNS respectively throughout this research project.

TABLE 1 Percentage (%) Removal of Methylene Blue at various pH for DRSP, $\lambda_{\text{max}}=780$

pH (T)	pHi	pHf	ΔpH	λ_{max}	ABS(Before)	ABS (After)	% Removal
3	7.30	7.38	1.61	540	2.595	0.293	88.70906
4	7.55	7.45	0.68	500	2.611	0.819	68.63271
5	7.65	7.41	-0.36	780	2.609	0.213	91.83595
6	7.68	7.46	-1.31	700	2.609	0.195	92.52587
7	7.73	7.42	-2.35	540	2.874	0.200	93.04106
8	7.64	7.28	-3.49	710	5.239	0.143	97.27047
9	7.66	7.42	-4.35	540	2.609	0.183	92.98582
10	7.70	7.3	-5.47	540	2.754	0.148	94.62600
11	7.75	7.4	-6.37	710	2.862	0.207	92.76730

TABLE 2: Percentage (%) Removal of Methylene Blue at various pH for BGNS, $\lambda_{\text{max}}=710$

pH (T)	pHi	pHf	ΔpH	λ_{max}	ABS (Before)	ABS (After)	% Removal
2	4.77	7.00	2.23	540	2.808	0.909	67.628205
3	7.30	7.04	-0.26	540	2.650	0.796	69.962264
4	7.55	7.08	-0.47	540	2.699	0.146	94.590589
5	7.65	7.08	-0.57	540	2.826	0.124	95.612173
6	7.68	7.04	-0.64	540	2.814	0.129	95.415778
7	7.73	7.10	-0.63	540	2.783	0.405	85.447359
8	7.64	6.98	-0.66	540	2.789	0.135	95.159555
9	7.66	7.06	-0.60	540	2.728	0.144	94.721408
10	7.75	7.15	-0.60	540	2.764	0.116	95.31840
11	7.7	7.04	-0.66	540	2.789	0.118	95.769093

Table 3: Effect of ionic strength for DRSP

Conc. NaNO_3 (M)	Absorbance BF	Absorbance A	% removal
0.2	2.052	0.758	63.060429
0.4	2.022	0.625	69.090010
0.6	2.017	0.553	72.583044
0.8	2.015	0.499	75.235732
1.0	2.009	0.493	75.460428
1.2	1.944	0.488	74.897119
1.4	1.957	0.457	76.647931
1.6	1.744	0.297	82.970183

Table 4: Effect of ionic strength for BGNS

Conc. NaNO_3 (M)	Absorbance BF	Absorbance A	% removal
0.2	2.093	1.095	47.6827520
0.4	1.975	0.459	76.7594936
0.6	1.938	0.440	77.2961816
0.8	1.939	0.458	76.3795771
1.0	1.855	0.516	72.1832884
1.2	1.946	0.562	71.1202467
1.4	1.939	0.464	76.0701393
1.6	1.918	0.530	72.367049

Figure 24: Plot of Intraparticle diffusion model for DRSP

Figure 25: Plot of Pseudo first order model for DRSP

Figure 26: plot of Pseudo second order model for DRSP

Figure 27: Plot of intraparticle diffusion model for BGNS

Figure 28: Plot of Pseudo first order model for BGNS

Figure 29: Plot of Pseudo second order isotherm for BGNS

3.5 Investigation of Kinetics Studies

the plot of Intraparticle diffusion model, Pseudo first order model, Pseudo second order model are shown in fig 24,25, 26 and 27 also 28 and 29 for testing kinetics data obtained for the adsorption of methylene blue dye on *Delonix regia* seed pod (DRSP) and Bambara ground nut shell (BGNS) respectively. Table 5 containing rate constant and coefficient of determination R^2 value obtained from these plots. The best fit for sorption kinetics data is Pseudo second order rate constant, K_2 as indicated by the coefficient of determination ($R^2=0.9975$ for DRSP and $R^2=0.9942$ for BGNS). The Pseudo second order rate constant (K_2) obtained for this adsorption process are $0.4027 \text{ gmin}^{-1}\text{mg}^{-1}$ for DRSP and $1.2296 \text{ gmin}^{-1}\text{mg}^{-1}$ for BGNS which is in agreed with the findings cited in the literature, Pseudo second order model best described the adsorption for methylene blue [23], adsorption of methylene blue was best described by Pseudo second order model [24], the assumption behind this model of adsorption process involves chemisorptions, which requires valence shell through the sharing or exchange of electrons between the adsorbent and the adsorbate [25].

Table 5:Rate constant and coefficient of determination of adsorption of methylene blue onto DRSP and BGNS.

	Intraparticle diffusion model		Pseudo first order model		Pseudo second order model	
	K_{id}	R^2	K_1	R^2	K_2	R^2
DRSP		0.0521	6.909×10^{-4}	0.0693	0.4027	0.9975
BGNS		0.483	1.948×10^{-3}	0.501	1.2296	0.9942

3.6 Equilibrium Studies

The results obtained on the adsorption of methylene blue onto the *Delonix regia* Seed Pod (DRSP) and Bambara Groundnut Shell (BGNS) were tested by different isotherm model as in the figures below. Fig 30, 31, 32 and 33 are the plots of amount of adsorbent, Langmuir adsorption isotherm, Freundlich adsorption isotherm and Tempkin adsorption isotherm respectively for DRSP and fig 34, 35, 36, and 37 for BGNS.

Figure 30: Plot of q_e against $(C_i - C_e)$ [DRSP]

Figure 31: Plot of $1/q_e$ against C_e [DRSP]

Figure 32: Plot of $\ln q_e$ against $\ln C_e$ [DRSP]

Figure 33: Plot of q_e against $\ln C_e$ [DRSP]

Figure 37: Plot of q_e (mg/l) against $\ln C_e$ [BGNS]

4. Conclusions

In this work, DRSP and BGNS powder are proved to be an efficient adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue dyes from aqueous solutions. The expensive adsorbents can be replaced by the low cost adsorbents for the removal of dyes from wastewater for industrial and water treatment plants. As presented in figures and tables above, various factors affect the adsorption capacity of DRSP and BGNS for the removal of methylene blue dyes contaminant. The removal of dye by adsorption on to agricultural by-product has been found to be useful means for controlling water pollution. Increase in pH, ionic strength, and contact time has an influenced on the removal of methylene blue dye contamination by DRSP and BGNS, the contact time is increased, the % removal increase, though at a point(saturation level), increasing time does not have any effect, pH 8 and 11 was found to be the optimal for DRSP and BGNS with λ_{\max} of 780nm and 710nm respectively. Finding also reveals that, percentage (%) removal increased with the increase in ionic strength. The outcome of the research confirmed 7.77 and 7.30 as point of zero charge (pzc) for DRSP and BGNS respectively.

Findings reveals that the data obtained was best fit the Pseudo Second Order Kinetics Isotherm with the coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.9975 and 0.9942 for DRSP and BGNS respectively and rate constant were found to be $0.4027 \text{ gmin}^{-1}\text{mg}^{-1}$ and $1.2296 \text{ gmin}^{-1}\text{mg}^{-1}$ for DRSP and BGNS respectively.

5. Recommendations

At the end of this research, it recommended that;

- More research should be carried out to treat industrial effluents using other low cost adsorbents and to demonstrate the technology effectively.
- Research should also be carried out using activated carbon prepared from DRSP and BGNS to improve the efficiency of removing toxic dyes from waste water.
- Further research should be done on removal of heavy metal using low cost agricultural waste from the aqueous solution, soil etc. to addressed health and environmental problems.
- The research work should be done on other alternative on removal of dyes contaminants such as Congo red, Crystal violet, Methylene orange, Rhodamine dye, heavy metals such as Pb, Fe, Co, Mn, Cr, Cd, Cu, Sb, etc. from the waste water.

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